

ANALYSIS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PREREQUISITES AND DIDACTICAL PRINCIPLES FOR TEACHING RKS SYNTAX

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to teaching Russian language syntax at the B1+ level, which requires a comprehensive approach that integrates psychological and didactic principles. The cognitive features of perceiving and mastering syntactic structures are analyzed, and modern teaching methods are highlighted. Special attention is paid to the adaptation of educational materials, the influence of emotional state on learning success, and the application of interactive technologies in the educational process. Based on the results of the analysis, practical recommendations were formulated aimed at increasing the efficiency of mastering complex syntactic constructions.

Keywords: communicative approach, didactic principles, systematicity, sequence, syntax, grammatical constructions, B1+ level, cognitive load, step-by-step complexity, adaptive learning, interactive methods, communicative situations, speech practice, motivation, emotional learning background

Introduction

Mastering Russian language syntax at the B1+ level is a crucial stage in developing linguistic competence, as at this level, students transition from using simple grammatical constructions to more complex and variable syntactic models. Mastering such structures requires not only a theoretical understanding of the rules but also practical skills in applying them in various contexts. At the same time, it is necessary to consider not only didactic principles but also psychological factors that influence the learning process.

One of the key factors determining the success of mastering complex syntactic constructions is the work of cognitive mechanisms. Studying foreign language grammar requires active involvement of memory, attention, analytical and synthetic thinking, as well as the ability to process and structure information. The individual characteristics of students' perception play a significant role in learning effectiveness, making it important to apply adaptive methodologies that account for cognitive load and various perception styles.

Psychological and didactic problem-based methods in teaching

Problem-based teaching methods represent a system of techniques and methods for organizing the educational process, in which students encounter a cognitive problem and are forced to seek its solution. These methods can be conventionally divided into psychological and didactic. The first is aimed at activating mental activity and developing cognitive processes, while the second focuses on the methodology of presenting material and developing skills for independent knowledge searching.

1. Psychological methods of problem-based learning

Psychological methods emphasize not transferring ready-made knowledge, but creating conditions in which students themselves strive to find solutions. Such an approach awakens

interest, stimulates mental activity, and develops research thinking. Let us consider the key methods used within this direction.

- Cognitive conflict method

One of the most effective methods for activating thinking is creating a conflict situation between existing knowledge and new information. A situation that does not meet the students' expectations is intentionally created before them. The goal of the method is to encourage students to actively seek an explanation.

- Method of posing problem-based questions

A problem question involves the possibility of finding the necessary answer to the given question from some set of these options or formulating the answer outside of this set. A question may contain a hidden contradiction and evoke various, sometimes opposing, positions during its resolution.

- Forecasting method

After interest arises and issues are actively discussed, it is important to learn how to identify patterns and predict the development of events. The essence of the method is to analyze already known data in order to predict the consequences, serving to form logical thinking.

- The method of creative problems

In concluding the block of psychological methods, one should highlight an approach in which students solve problems that do not have standard solutions. The essence lies in setting open creative tasks that require a creative approach and the development of non-standard thinking.

When moving from students' internal motivation to organizing the educational process itself, it is logical to consider **didactic methods** that help structure problem-based learning.

2. Didactic methods of problem-based learning

While psychological methods are aimed at stimulating cognitive activity, didactic methods ensure the correct organization of learning activities aimed at the conscious and firm assimilation of knowledge. Let us consider the main ones.

- Problematic presentation of the material

Sometimes students are not ready to formulate the problem independently. In this case, the initiative passes to the teacher. The teacher poses the problem themselves and demonstrates the ways to solve it step by step. Teaches schoolchildren to follow the logic of reasoning and to construct it independently.

- Heuristic (partial-search) method

This method takes the next step toward independence. Students are involved in solving the problem, receiving guidance from the teacher. Students propose hypotheses, and the teacher helps them find the right path.

- Research method

By continuing to increase the level of independence, one can transition to a research method that approximates real scientific activity. Students independently undergo all stages of research: from setting the task to analyzing the results obtained. Serves to develop research skills.

- Problem Situations Method

In concluding the didactic block, let's consider a method that allows for connecting knowledge with real life. Students are asked to consider a life or hypothetical problem that requires a

comprehensive approach. The goal is to teach how to apply knowledge in non-standard conditions. Problem-based learning methods allow for making the educational process more meaningful and motivating. **Psychological methods** foster cognitive interest and activate thinking.

Didactic methods structure the learning process, helping students master the material consciously. Their competent combination contributes to the development of analytical thinking, independence, and research skills.

Discussion

It is considered that the mental development of a child, like the holistic development of a person, is carried out simultaneously along the following lines: the cognitive sphere (establishment of intelligence, development of cognitive mechanisms); the psychological structure and content of activity (establishment of goals, motives, and development of their correlation, mastery of methods and means of activity); personality (orientation, value orientation, self-awareness, self-esteem, interaction with the social environment, etc.). [4; P.97]. And L.S. Vygotsky's ideas provide an important clarification: he emphasized that mental development represents the comprehensive formation of the individual as a whole. Under the social situation of development, he understood a special form of the child's interaction with social reality, into which activity as a method of realizing these relations is necessarily included. [1; P.17]. Thus, development and learning are interconnected and determined by the individual characteristics of the student. In this context, such systemic psychological education as individual

style of students' educational and cognitive activity (ESPA). SPI is considered a psychological mechanism for students and schoolchildren to master knowledge, skills, and abilities, the formation of which is one of the important reserves for increasing learning efficiency. As a synonym for ISPD, the concept of "cognitive style" is often used (in foreign psychology) [4; P.475].

Cognitive development is the gradual formation of a child's intellect. At various stages, cognitive disorders associated with perinatal nervous system lesions, early-life diseases, psychosocial, and other factors can be encountered. The classification of cognitive development periods is based on the ability to interact increasingly meaningfully with the surrounding world and other people [7].

Research indicates that the level of cognitive load increases when perceiving complex sentences with a subordinate clause, requiring specific learning strategies. For example, a sentence:

Although the weather was cool, we still decided to go for a walk, as we hadn't seen each other for a long time and wanted to discuss important matters.

This complex sentence requires the student to retain several subordinate parts in their memory and understand their semantic connections.

To facilitate the assimilation of complex syntactic constructions, it is important to apply methods aimed at reducing cognitive load. They help students gradually adapt to more complex grammatical structures, minimizing memory overload and ensuring systematic mastery of the material.

One such method is breaking complex sentences into simpler elements and analyzing them in stages. This allows students to identify the key components of the construction by mastering them sequentially. This approach contributes to a deeper understanding of the logical connections within the sentence and reduces cognitive load.

Using tables and diagrams to visually represent sentence structure provides additional support in the learning process. Graphic representation of grammatical constructions helps students more quickly identify patterns, structure information, and apply acquired knowledge meaningfully. This method is particularly effective for students who perceive material in a visual form more easily.

It is also important to consider the students' level of preparation and to apply a gradual increase in the complexity of the grammatical material. The sequential introduction of new constructions without sudden complications ensures the smooth development of linguistic skills and contributes to a stronger assimilation of knowledge.

The comprehensive application of these methods facilitates the perception of material, making the process of studying complex syntactic structures more accessible and effective.

When organizing the foreign language teaching process, it is also important to consider the individual characteristics of information perception. Each student processes material differently, depending on the prevailing cognitive style. Understanding these differences allows for the adaptation of teaching methodology, making it more effective and comfortable for each student. An individual approach is the development of the strengths and talents of each individual student. This approach is a principle in pedagogy embodied in the management of human development, aimed at knowing the traits of an individual [2; P. 30]. And I.M. Osmolovskaya believes that "individualization is a variant of differentiation in which the educational process is conducted taking into account the characteristics of each individual student. Differentiation refers to a method of organizing the educational process that takes into account the individual typological characteristics of the individual (abilities, interests, inclinations, features of intellectual activity, etc.)" [3; P.8]. In foreign language teaching methodology, three main styles of information perception are distinguished:

Visual style - students "think through images and most successfully perceive information presented through visual images. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to this teaching style, i.e., to use visual images, graphics, images, diagrams, and written speech" [6; P.183].

Audial style - information is better perceived through hearing, so listening to dialogues, speaking, and repeating grammatical constructions play an important role. Audials have excellent memory and a surprisingly sharp hearing. When interacting, sound perception is important for such people. They respond to voice volume, timbre, and intonation; meanwhile, looks and touches are in the background [8].

Kinestical style - students need active interaction with the material, including tactile sensations, practical tasks, and role-playing games.

The process of mastering complex grammatical structures requires consideration of cognitive mechanisms and individual characteristics of information perception. Using adaptive strategies aimed at reducing cognitive load, as well as methods suitable for different learning styles, makes learning grammar more effective and engaging. The development of analytical

thinking, conscious perception of linguistic patterns, and an interactive approach contribute to the firm assimilation of syntactic constructions and the formation of stable skills in their use.

One of the important factors influencing the success of mastering complex syntactic constructions is motivation. It is this that determines the level of students' involvement in the educational process and their striving to achieve the set goals. V. S. Vygotsky asserts: "High internal and external motivation contributes to the accelerated formation of linguistic skills, as well as increasing the ability to long-term memorize complex grammatical structures" [1; C.95]. At the same time, motivation does not exist in isolation—its level is significantly influenced by the emotional background of learning. If the educational environment causes stress or anxiety in students, their cognitive resources are spent not only on learning the material but also on overcoming psychological discomfort. As a result, the assimilation of new knowledge may slow down. On the contrary, a positive emotional state contributes to a reduction in anxiety levels and the creation of a comfortable educational environment. Creating such an environment is possible through several factors. First, it is important for the teacher to use encouragement and supportive feedback, as this strengthens students' confidence in their abilities and encourages them to work actively with the material. Secondly, it is necessary to introduce game and interactive elements into the learning process, as they contribute to increasing interest in the language and make the assimilation of syntactic constructions more natural and effortless. Third, the formation of a positive emotional background is possible through the creation of a collaborative atmosphere where mistakes are perceived not as failures, but as a natural part of the learning process. The combination of high motivation and emotional comfort plays a decisive role in mastering syntax. The optimal combination of these factors not only increases the effectiveness of learning grammatical constructions but also makes the process itself more engaging, which ultimately contributes to better material assimilation and the formation of confidence in language use.

The application of effective methods for teaching Russian language syntax requires adherence to a number of didactic principles that ensure the systematicity, sequence, and practical orientation of the educational process. Successful mastery of syntactic constructions is possible through a comprehensive approach that combines traditional and modern teaching methods.

The first didactic principle is consistency and systematicity. The sequential study of syntax involves a gradual transition from simple constructions to more complex ones, ensuring fluid learning and contributing to the expansion of students' linguistic repertoire. At the same time, it is important to consider not only grammatical aspects but also the specifics of using various structures in real communicative situations. The gradual complication of material contributes to better assimilation, allowing students to apply new knowledge consciously. This approach minimizes overload and creates favorable conditions for the natural inclusion of complex syntactic constructions into speech.

Also, for the formation of strong syntax skills, it is important to integrate the language into real communicative situations. Theoretical knowledge of grammatical rules must be reinforced by their active use in speech. It should be noted that the effectiveness of mastering syntactic constructions largely depends on the forms of educational activity that stimulate the active use of language in real or near-real conditions. In this context, **interactive teaching**

methods aimed at developing communicative competence and creative thinking acquire particular value.

Interaction eliminates the dominance of both one speaker and one opinion over another. During dialogic learning, students learn to think critically, solve complex problems based on the analysis of circumstances and relevant information, weigh alternative opinions, make well-thought-out decisions, participate in discussions, and communicate with other people [5; C.51]. For this purpose, various forms of learning activities are organized in lessons: individual, pair, and group work, research projects, role-playing games, and creative tasks are implemented. It is through such activities that students gain the opportunity not only to reinforce the studied structures but also to integrate them into their own speech practice. This makes the learning process more natural, meaningful, and productive, contributing to the formation of sustainable language skills.

This approach allows students not only to memorize syntactic structures but also to understand their functionality, which ultimately contributes to more confident and free speech.

Interactive methods, such as virtual simulations, chatbots for syntax practice, and online courses, facilitate the comprehension of complex material and create conditions for independent study. Additionally, augmented and virtual reality technologies can be used, which help visualize syntactic constructions and the context in which they are applied. The application of virtual reality in foreign language teaching facilitates better memorization of grammatical structures through engagement in an interactive environment. Thanks to these technologies, students can interact with syntactic models in real time, which increases awareness of their use.

Another promising direction is the gamification of the educational process. Including game elements such as quizzes, scoring systems, and quests contributes to increasing student motivation and engagement. Interactive tasks with competition elements allow students to better memorize complex syntactic constructions and apply them in practice.

Also, an important aspect of the modern approach to learning is adaptive learning, where digital platforms analyze student progress and adapt tasks to their individual level. This method allows for the optimization of the educational process and the concentration of attention on those aspects that cause the greatest difficulties.

Teaching syntax plays a key role in developing linguistic competence, as proficiency in syntactic constructions is essential for successful speech formation. The effectiveness of mastering grammatical material depends on the methodological approaches used in educational practice. One of the fundamental principles is the principle of consistency and systematicity. This approach ensures the logical assimilation of syntactic constructions, promotes their conscious use in speech, and minimizes difficulties associated with mastering complex grammatical structures.

The essence of the sequence principle is that the study of syntax should proceed in stages: from simple constructions to more complex ones. This method helps students adapt to new grammatical models, reducing the risk of overload and errors. The principle of systematicity assumes that learning is built upon already acquired knowledge. New syntactic structures are not studied in isolation, but are included in the general system of the language, which helps to better understand their functions and relationships. The gradual introduction of more complex material contributes to a deeper assimilation, as it allows students to

consciously apply the acquired knowledge. Effective mastery of syntactic structures requires a thoroughly thought-out training program that includes the gradual complication of the material. At the initial stage, students are introduced to simple narrative sentences and the main principles of coordinating subject and predicate. This creates a solid foundation for further study of syntax.

After mastering the basic models, students move on to studying compound and complex sentences: studying conjunctions (and, but, or, etc.), and exercises on transforming simple sentences into complex ones.

In the final stage, students master complex sentences with various types of subordinate clauses (explanatory, determinative, adverbial).

Example transformation:

Simple sentence: *I am reading a book.*

Expanded sentence: *I am reading an interesting book in the library.*

Complex sentence: *I am reading a book my friend recommended to me.*

The principle of systematicity implies the integration of new knowledge into the already existing language system, making learning more meaningful. One of the key aspects of its implementation is the connection with previous topics: before studying complex sentences, students must confidently master subordinate conjunctions, and to master passive constructions, it is necessary to first study the active forms of verbs. The use of reference diagrams and tables also plays an important role, as they help to visually represent syntactic structures and better understand their internal organization. Furthermore, the systematic nature of instruction presupposes a connection between syntax and real speech practice; therefore, to reinforce the material, students must actively apply the studied constructions in dialogues, essays, and discussions.

To effectively implement the principles of consistency and systematicity in teaching syntax, various methodological techniques are applied, allowing students to gradually master and reinforce grammatical constructions. One such technique is the step-by-step complexity method, which involves the sequential addition of new elements: first, simple sentences are studied, then compound and complex constructions are introduced, which avoids overload and contributes to the gradual assimilation of material.

Additionally, the method of sentence transformation is applied, where students learn to transform simple sentences into complex ones and replace individual parts of syntactic constructions with synonymous expressions. This helps to better understand sentence structure and expand the language repertoire.

The method of juxtaposition is also an effective tool, allowing for the analysis and comparison of various types of sentences, as well as the identification of their features and patterns. This approach helps students consciously perceive grammatical differences and correctly use constructions in speech.

Finally, the method of communicative situations plays an important role, in which syntactic constructions are applied in real speech contexts. Writing letters, participating in debates, and oral narratives help integrate studied structures into active speech, making learning more meaningful and practice-oriented. The comprehensive use of these techniques contributes to the effective mastery of syntax and the development of communicative skills.

Results

Syntax instruction is not merely the study of rules and structures, but a process of forming a conscious and competent command of the language. The principles of sequence and systematicity allow for the construction of learning in such a way that new knowledge organically fits into the already formed linguistic framework, ensuring a smooth and logical transition from simple constructions to complex ones.

A comprehensive approach, including the method of step-by-step complication, sentence transformation, comparison, and modeling of real communicative situations, makes the process of studying syntax not only effective but also practice-oriented. It is important not only to analyze theoretical aspects but also to apply them in speech, which contributes to a deeper assimilation of the material.

Thus, a competent command of syntax forms the foundation for the confident and accurate expression of thoughts, develops analytical thinking, and develops linguistic intuition. Sequential and systematic learning not only facilitates the process of mastering complex grammatical constructions but also makes language a tool for effective communication in any field of life.

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